

The TOM Toolkit Development and Observing Program

Bryan Miller, Cesar Briceño, Stephen Ridgway, and Rachel Street

Astronomy has entered the era of time-domain astronomy (TDA), enabled by large, multi-epoch sky surveys. Efforts such as the SDSS series of surveys, Pan-STARRS, Skymapper, the Dark Energy Survey (DES), DECaLS, Gaia, and the Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF) have already generated petabyte-scale datasets and alerts of transient sources. The Vera C. Rubin Observatory is under construction on Cerro Pachón in Chile, and its 10-year Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) (www.lsst.org) will begin in just a few years. LSST will produce thousands of alerts every few minutes from variable stars, AGNs, Solar System bodies, all varieties of cosmic explosions, and transients of as yet unknown forms (Ridgway et al., 2014, ApJ, 796, 53). It will also produce extremely deep images of the entire southern sky and catalogs of billions of static and variable sources. This data set will be useful to all fields of astrophysics. Astronomers will mine the catalogs and compile very large samples of objects for further study. It will not be possible to understand the nature of many of these detections from LSST photometry alone, so additional, or follow-up, observations will be required.

The detection of an electromagnetic counterpart (kilonova explosion) to a gravitational-wave event and the association of a high-energy neutrino detection with an active galaxy shows the power of multi-messenger astronomy (MMA). Combining information from different messengers (gravitational waves, neutrinos, high-energy particles, and electromagnetic radiation) collected on short timescales allows us to understand the nature of the sources

and the physical processes involved. In the era of TDA and MMA, timely follow-up, often requiring rapid response, with a multiplicity of flexibly scheduled observing facilities is essential, and the demand is growing.

MMA is one of the National Science Foundation (NSF) Ten Big Ideas. It unifies the capabilities and results from some of the NSF's major astrophysics facilities (e.g., LIGO, IceCube, Rubin Observatory, Gemini, KPNO, CTIO, and SOAR) to discover and characterize new and rare events. The NSF-sponsored report by the National Research Council, *Optimizing the U.S. Ground-Based Optical and Infrared Astronomy System* (Elmegreen et al. 2015), recommends that NSF facilities coordinate to optimize Rubin Observatory follow-up. Similar capabilities are needed for MMA follow-up.

The sheer volume of alerts and the sizes of the survey catalogs mean that traditional methods that rely on human review for classifying and sorting cannot be applied to this scale. If the process of classifying and responding to the LSST alert stream cannot keep up with the data rate, then many interesting targets could be missed. The process of classifying sources and executing observations must be automated. The system that the community is developing to accomplish this automation is shown in Figure 1. The system is a set of tools and an envisioned workflow that operates within a time allocation process. Observing projects for following up alerts or studying selected objects from survey catalogs must still be approved by time allocation committees (TAC).

The main components of the follow-up system are the following:

1. Alert Broker: This accepts transient event alerts from one or more surveys and tries to classify the object.
2. Target Observation Manager (TOM): This is a target and observation management tool for specific research projects.
3. Interfaces and Schedulers: Facilities must have programmatic interfaces to receive observation requests and return status. The schedulers dynamically create the observing plans for the telescopes on the network in real time. There can be a single network scheduler, or individual telescopes can have their own schedulers.
4. Telescopes: These are the individual nodes of the network. They must be able to broadcast their current observing status (closed, open, current target), receive observation plans from the scheduler, and execute the observations.
5. Data-reduction pipelines: These reduce the data immediately after they are taken. Both raw and processed data are transferred to an archive.
6. Data archives: These are databases for the raw and reduced data. Authenticated users (often TOMs) can download the data as soon as it is available.

The brokers classify transient alerts based on all available information, e.g., position, color, and light-curve information. Catalog matching and artificial intelligence algorithms are often used. Users can define search filters in order to extract objects of interest. There are several ongoing broker projects including NOIRLab’s ANTARES (<https://www.noao.edu/ANTARES>), Chile’s ALERCE (<http://alerce.science>), and the United Kingdom’s Lasair (<https://github.com/lst-uk/lasair>).

The Target Observation Managers (TOMs) are a key component of the envisioned system since they are a core tool of the science teams. It is expected that different projects will have their own TOMs, which contain the “science logic” of these projects that will help prioritize the targets culled by the brokers and allow the teams to request observations on the facilities on which they have been

awarded time (Street et al. 2018, SPIE, 1070711). TOMs are modern and highly capable bookkeeping tools that enable scientists to keep up with large and constant streams of targets, but they can also be used for data reduction, visualization, and access management. Various projects have created and used TOMs for studying supernovae, AGN, microlensing events, and Solar System objects, among other targets (<https://www.noao.edu/meetings/lst-tds/>). Each of these was a bespoke system developed independently even though they share common functionality. Since they are unique and developed by astronomers, they are also time-consuming to produce and maintain.

Any telescope facility that has application programming interfaces (APIs) for communicating with the TOMs can participate in the ecosystem shown in Figure 1. However, there are advantages to networks of telescopes for sharing time and/or coordinating observations. Projects

Figure 1: The developing alert and survey follow-up system. The components are described more fully in the text. NOIRLab is involved in developing an alert broker (ANTARES), and NOIRLab telescope facilities are part of the Astronomical Event Observatory Network (AEON) collaboration. The scope of AEON is outlined in yellow. The red, blue, and black arrows indicate where APIs are required for communication between the different components of the systems. Participation in AEON is not required to be part of the overall ecosystem. (Figure concept: Rachel Street, Las Cumbres Observatory)

MMA is one of the National Science Foundation's (NSF) Ten Big Ideas.

that have targets with a wide range of brightnesses, e.g., SNe, can make use of telescopes of different apertures. Telescopes distributed in longitude allow follow-up at any time and can provide near-continuous coverage.

The Astronomical Event Observatory Network (AEON; <http://ast.nao.edu/data/aeon>) is a collaboration between the member observatories, currently Las Cumbres Observatory and NOIRLab, to develop observatory capabilities and procedures for supporting this follow-up network. It has been focused on dynamical scheduling capabilities, interfaces, and data reduction and archiving. Las Cumbres is already a network of 0.4m, 1m, and 2m telescopes. AEON adds telescopes of larger apertures. The progress on SOAR dynamical scheduling is described in an accompanying article. The TDA project of the Gemini in the Era of Multi-Messenger Astronomy (GEMMA) program (www.gemini.edu/gemma/index.html) will further develop APIs, a dynamic scheduler, and real-time data reduction to provide Gemini with equivalent capabilities. In the future, additional telescopes such as the CTIO Victor M. Blanco 4m Telescope may join the network. Other observatories have also expressed interest in joining and may be added once

technical details of how the network will function have been finalized.

In order to make TOMs easier to develop and maintain, the Las Cumbres Observatory built on their staff's experience with early TOMs to create a professionally-developed TOM Toolkit (<https://tom-toolkit.readthedocs.io>). The toolkit provides common functionality such as database creation and interfaces to alert brokers, telescope facilities, and archives. It is designed to be easy to install and customize.

In 2019, Las Cumbres initiated the TOM Toolkit Development and Observing program to promote community use and development of the TOM Toolkit and the fledgling follow-up system. Las Cumbres offered 1000 hours of time on their 1m telescope network, and both SOAR and Gemini Observatory (both operated by NOIRLab) contributed 50 hours each. Las Cumbres also raised approximately \$250,000 from the Heising-Simons Foundation and the Zegar Foundation to fund TOM development via a competitive proposal process. The funds are being distributed by the LSST Corporation.

In the lead-up to the proposal deadline, interested teams attended a workshop at the Carnegie Observatories

Figure 2: Attendees of the TOM Toolkit Workshop attend a tutorial on customizing the toolkit for their needs.

Table 1. Observatory and Over-subscription Factors

Observatory	Las Cumbres	SOAR	Gemini South	Gemini North
Hours Requested	3210	199	110	225
Over-subscription	3.2	4.0	6.7	

in Pasadena, California, between 30 September and 04 October 2019 (<https://tom-toolkit.readthedocs.io>). Over 40 participants learned about the capabilities of the participating facilities and how to use and modify the TOM Toolkit. Some participants in deep concentration during one of the tutorials are shown in Figure 2.

Thirty-three proposals were received, and the over-subscription factor for the NOIRLab-operated facilities was over 4 (see Table 1). The proposals covered supernovae and gravitational wave follow-up to microlensing, exoplanets, and the Solar System. Most were time-domain proposals, but this was not a requirement. A single TAC consisting of experts in both the science topics of the proposals and the facilities evaluated the proposals. The result is that four projects were awarded time on Gemini, five projects on SOAR, and fourteen on the Las Cumbres network. Seven of the projects received development funding with the largest award being \$45,000. The teams are currently developing

their TOMs. The programs will run through the end of the ZTF public survey in December 2020.

The TOM Toolkit proposal opportunity is not only an early end-to-end test of the system in Figure 1 but also a trial of a possible TAC process and observing procedures for AEON. The AEON participants are discussing new ways of allocating time to simplify the process for PIs and promote the use and capabilities of the network. By default, the current proposal processes will be used, but alternatives that will make it easier to apply for time on the network and reduce multiple jeopardy are being considered.

While the system described here is designed mainly for automating alert follow-up, many of the tools such as TOMs and facility APIs, schedulers, and data reduction/archiving, will be of great value to a wide variety of projects, especially those with large numbers of targets and those that would benefit from automation. Updates on the status of the system will be given in future newsletters.